

PAIN-FREE AND MOTOR DYSFUNCTION ON LOWER EXTREMITY IN AORTIC DISSECTION: A CASE REPORT

Keywords

Pain-free,

Motor dysfunction,

Aortic dissection.

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ABSTRACT

Aortic dissection and cerebrovascular accidents are among the most life-threatening diseases in the emergency department. This patient was sent to us with a preliminary diagnosis of the Cerebro vasküler accident from an external center with the complaint of weakness in the right lower extremity. In the examination of the patient, aortic dissection was detected in the examinations performed due to the coldness in the right lower extremity leading to other differential diagnoses. Pain-free dissection cases in the literature are manifested by neurological symptoms. As in our case, in patients who detect common symptoms of different diseases, serial examination provides early diagnosis to reduce mortality and morbidity.

INTRODUCTION

Aortic dissection was a mortal condition on emergency medicine. The incidence of aortic dissection in the world population is between 2.6 to 3.5 per 100,000 people .^{1,2}

The main classification in anatomic was type A and type B on the Stanford systems. Type A of aortic dissection started from ascending aorta and may progress to the arch and thoracoabdominal part. Type B of aortic dissection started from descending aorta and may progress distal part. Type A is more severe and mortal than type B.³

The basic pathophysiologic mechanism of aortic dissection is shearing stress and damaged endothelial cells. The first event in aortic dissection disjunction to intima from the media layer .^{4,5} All symptoms were observed from the disjunctional part of the vessels. When the disjunctional part of the ascending aorta, the main symptom can be myocardial ischemia .⁶ When the disjunctional part is on the renal artery, observed renal infarction.⁷ We present an important case of type b aortic dissection.

CASE

A 69-year-old male patient was admitted to weakness right lower extremity in the external emergency department. On external ED examination, was observed the cerebrovascular accident and transport to a more qualified hospital emergency department. However, the patient had diabetes mellitus and hypertension and used metformin, furosemide. And the patient said had a little back pain. In vital signs was observed blood oxygen saturation 97%, blood pressure was 130/70 mmHg and heartbeats was 100/min. Respiratory rates were tachypneic, 18/min.

On physical examination, the patient was awake, oriented, coopered. Glasgow coma score was

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15/15. No deficit on cranial nerves. There was no lateralization. Pupil reflexes were normal.

In Cardiac, thoracic, and abdominal examinations could be found no phatologic signs and symptoms.

In our investigation, we found a weakness and thermal dysregulation at the right lower extremity. Two lower extremities had different temperatures. On lower extremities, there was no result on Homans tests, no ecchymosis, and no pallor.

In electrocardiography, there was no ST elevation, it was sinus rhythm. Heart rate was bradycardiac, 49/min.

In biochemical test, white blood cells was $8 \times 10^3/\text{mm}^3$, hemogram was 15,2, platelets counts 180000 in mm^3 , high-sensitive cardiac troponin was negative. The aspartate amino transpherase was 42 U/L, creatinin was 1,07 and blood urea nitrogen (BUN) 22mg/dl. CRP: 5,1mg/dl (0-5)

The Field Assessment Stroke Triage for Emergency Destination (FAST-ED) was low.

It was taken computed tomography angiography (CTA) and observed type 2 dissection, seeing seperated layer of intima and media beetwen the aortic arc to the right iliac artery (Figure 1.)

The patient was consulted to the Cardiovascular Surgery department. The patient had been hospitalized for endovascular aneurysm repair.

In operation, there was no problem. After the operation, the aneurysm is repaired, the leg circulation was normal. After one week, there was a postoperative complication, wound infection. It was consulted reconstructive surgery department and use cefazoline.

Figure 1: Computed Tomography Angiograph

DISCUSSION

Aortic dissection is a mortal disease and it must be determined by a fast diagnosis. Type 2 aortic dissections have a lot of types of different symptoms. For example; if it is located at the renal artery, there will be observed renal infarctions.

A cerebrovascular accident is an embolism on the brain vascular system and infarctions of some neurons. If the infarctions is located on the pre-central gyrus, the motor cortex will be damaged and there will be some motor dysfunctions.

Sometimes, different conditions have the same symptoms. All clinicians must be careful about the emergency diagnosis. An important and rare example was our case.

Pain-free dissections observed with neurologic symptoms. And the aort dissection can be difficult and delayed diagnosis on pain-free dissections. ⁸ Aortic dissection and cerebrovascular accident, which are the most important life-threatening diseases in the emergency department, can sometimes be confused with symptoms. Aortic dissection should be considered especially in cases of muscle weakness or blurred consciousness, back pain, coldness in the extremities, and no pulse. ⁹In our case, at the first look, it has seen some symptoms for cerebrovascular accidents on the second look, the lower extremity had vascular problems and paleness. In CTA, there was a type 2 aortic dissection.

CONCLUSION

Repeated examinations are important for early diagnosis in patients with same symptoms of life-threatening diseases. Early diagnosis reduces mortality and morbidity in these patients.

Conflict of interest

No conflict of interest is reported by the authors.

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No

REFERENCES

1. Hagan, P.G., et al., The International Registry of Acute Aortic Dissection (IRAD): new insights into an old disease. *JAMA*, 2000. 283(7): 897-903.
2. Melvindottir, I.H., et al., The incidence and mortality of acute thoracic aortic dissection: results from a whole nation study. *Eur J Cardiothorac Surg*, 2016. 50(6): 1111-1117.
3. Lombardi, J.V., et al., Society for Vascular Surgery (SVS) and Society of Thoracic Surgeons (STS) Reporting Standards for Type B Aortic Dissections. *Ann Thorac Surg*, 2020. 109(3): 959-981.
4. Chi, Q., et al., Numerical analysis of wall shear stress in ascending aorta before tearing in type A aortic dissection. *Comput Biol Med*, 2017. 89: 236-247.

5. Osswald, A., et al., Elevated Wall Shear Stress in Aortic Type B Dissection May Relate to Retrograde Aortic Type A Dissection: A Computational Fluid Dynamics Pilot Study. *Eur J Vasc Endovasc Surg*, 2017. 54(3): 324-330.
6. Wu, B.T., C.Y. Li, and Y.T. Chen, Type A Aortic Dissection Presenting with Inferior ST-Elevation Myocardial Infarction. *Acta Cardiol Sin*, 2014. 30(3):248-52.
7. Renaud, S., et al., Spontaneous renal artery dissection with renal infarction. *Clin Kidney J*, 2012. 5(3): 261-4.
8. Gaul, C., W. Dietrich, and F.J. Erbguth, Neurological symptoms in aortic dissection: a challenge for neurologists. *Cerebrovasc Dis*, 2008. 26(1): 1-8.
9. Walma, R.A., F.H. Vermeij, and S. Bakker, [Neurological signs in aortic dissection]. *Ned Tijdschr Geneesk*, 2013. 157(38): 6259.